

Genome sequences of plant associated *Rhodococcus* spp. isolates from Tunisia

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Abstract

Phytopathogenic isolates of *Rhodococcus* spp. are known to cause disease on herbaceous and woody species (Putnam and Miller, 2007; Miller and Putnam 2010). In 2011, two distinct *Rhodococcus* species designated as PBTS1 and PBTS2 caused serious losses to the pistachio industry in California and Arizona (Stamler et al, 2015a, b, 2016). On ornamental plants, major disease symptoms caused by *R. fascians* were described as leafy galls and stems fasciations (Stes et al. 2013), while on woody trees the symptoms included stunted growth and proliferation of misshapen shoots known as witches's brooms (Stamler et al, 2015a, b). The virulence strategy employed by the renowned *R. fascians* D188 consists of the disruption of plant hormone balance through the production and modulation of cytokinins and auxins (Pertry et al, 2009, 2010). The genes that are essential for cytokinin biosynthesis and modification are encoded by three virulence loci clustered on the *fas* operon which is located on a linear plasmid of *R. fascians* (Crespi et al, 1992; Francis et al, 2012). Complete genome and plasmid sequences for *R. fascians* D188 were previously reported (Francis et al, 2012; Creason et al, 2014) as well as the two pistachio *Rhodococcus* PBTS 1 and PBTS 2 isolates (Stamler et al, 2016). Four distinct *Rhodococcus* species isolates from symptomatic almond rootstocks, pistachio tree and ornamental plants in Tunisia were used in this study. The ornamental *Rhodococcus* isolate B10 was shown to cause stunting and shoot proliferation on *Iresine herbestii* plants in pathogenicity assays (Dhaouadi et al, 2019). The two almond *Rhodococcus* isolates GS6 and SB10 and the pistachio *Rhodococcus* isolate K5 developed shoot proliferation and stunting on both the host of origin and the pea seedlings bioassays (Unpublished data). It is well known that the population structure of *R. fascians* tends to be diverse from one host to another and from a region to another (Creason et al, 2014). Here, we provide a first insight into the genetic diversity of phytopathogenic *Rhodococcus* in Tunisia through the genome sequencing and assemblies of four isolates collected from pistachio, almond and the ornamental plant *Iresine herbestii*.

Materials and methods

Bacterial isolates used

We used four distinct *Rhodococcus* isolates from symptomatic plant materials collected in Tunisia: one isolate (B10) from ornamental plant causing infection on *Iresine herbestii*, two (GS6 and SB10) from almond rootstock and one (K5) from pistachio plant.

Growth conditions

Bacterial cultures were grown at 27 °C on agar plates of D2 medium containing glucose 10.0 g l⁻¹, casein hydrolysate 4.0 g l⁻¹, yeast extract 2.0 g l⁻¹, NH₄Cl 1.0 g l⁻¹, MgSO₄·7H₂O 0.3 g l⁻¹, LiCl 5.0 g l⁻¹, tris (hydroxymethyl) aminomethane 1.2 g l⁻¹, and 15 g l⁻¹ agar supplemented with 40 mg l⁻¹ polymyxin B sulfate and 0.5 mg l⁻¹ sodium azide.

Sequencing of bacterial genomic DNA

Genomic DNA sequences from the bacterial isolates were acquired using a sequencing service provider named MicrobesNG (Birmingham, UK, <https://microbesng.com>). A protocol supplied by MicrobesNG was followed to ship the bacterial samples. Briefly, a single colony of bacterial culture was transferred to a tube containing 25 ml D2 liquid medium and the culture was grown in a shaking incubator set at 27 °C temperature and 1500 rpm speed until the OD₆₀₀ was reached between 0.25-0.50. The culture was centrifuged at 4000 x g for 10 min and the supernatant was discarded. The pellet was resuspended in 500 µl cryopreservant liquid supplied by MicrobesNG. Resuspended cells were transferred to the barcoded bead tube; the tubes were sealed, and sent to MicrobesNG for DNA extraction and sequencing by Illumina technology. The protocol used by MicrobesNG is briefly described here: Three beads were washed with extraction buffer containing lysozyme and RNase A, incubated for 25 min at 37 °C. Proteinase K and RNaseA were added and incubated for 5 min at 65 °C. Genomic DNA was purified using an equal volume of SPRI beads (abm, Richmond, Canada) and resuspended in EB buffer. DNA was quantified in triplicates with the Quantit dsDNA HS assay in an Ependorff AF2200 plate reader. Genomic DNA libraries were prepared using Nextera XT Library Prep Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA) following the manufacturer's protocol with the following modifications: two nanograms of DNA instead of one were used as input, and PCR elongation time was increased to 1 min from 30 seconds. DNA quantification and library preparation were carried out on a Hamilton Microlab STAR automated liquid handling system. Pooled libraries were quantified using the Kapa Biosystems Library Quantification Kit for Illumina on a Roche light cycler 96 qPCR machine. Libraries were sequenced on the Illumina HiSeq using a 250bp paired end protocol. The reads were trimmed using Trimmomatic version 0.39 (Bolger et al, 2014) with a sliding window quality cutoff of Q15 and the quality was assessed using in-house scripts combined with Samtools version 1.4 (<git://github.com/samtools/samtools.git>), BedTools version 2.18 (Quinlan and Hall, 2010) and bwa-mem (Li and Durbin, 2009) software. Sequence reads were assembled into contigs using Quast software version 5.0.2 (Gurevich et al, 2013). The genomes were annotated with Prokka 1.14.3 (<https://github.com/tseemann/prokka>), protein-coding features and tRNA were predicted using Prodigal version 2.6 (Hyatt et al, 2010) and rRNA was predicted by ARAGORN version 1.2 (Laslett and Canback, 2004). We have implemented a quality control test for bacterial genomes using average nucleotide identity (ANI) against the genomes of the type strains of *Rhodococcus* available in GenBank (Ciufo et al, 2018).

Results

We sequenced the genomes of four isolates of *Rhodococcus* spp. isolated from different hosts of almond, pistachio and the ornamental plant *Iresine herbstii*. One isolate (B10) was obtained from diseased *Iresine herbstii* in Tunisia (Dhaouadi et al, 2019). The sequence reads assembled by Quast revealed a number of contigs ranging from 128 to 205 with the largest contigs of 352664 bp. The contigs of the genome assemblies of our four strains SB10, GS6, B10 and K5 add up to 5,508,857 bp; 5,427,417 bp; 5,469,932 bp and 4,030,995 bp, respectively, with a GC content of 64.39%, 64.56%, 65.11% and 70.26% respectively. The

total number of genes including the protein-coding genes, tRNA and tmRNA genes for each isolate is listed in Table 1. The results based on the ANI test and current taxonomic nomenclature revealed an identity over 90% of the submitted genome sequence to *Rhodococcus* species. The sequence of isolate K5 genome is 97.9% identical to the type genome of *Rhodococcus kroppenstedtii*, isolate B10 genome is identical to multiple species of *Rhodococcus* type genomes but low identity to any specific species, isolate SB10 genome is 97.7% identical to *Rhodococcus fascians* NBRC 12155, and isolate GS6 genome is 97.8% identical to *Rhodococcus fascians* NBRC 12155.

Data availability. This whole-genome shotgun has been deposited at DDBJ/ENA/GenBank under accession numbers JAAFYU000000000, JAAFYV000000000, JAAFYW000000000 and JAAFYX000000000. The versions described in this paper are JAAFYU010000000, JAAFYV010000000, JAAFYW010000000 and JAAFYX010000000. Raw sequence reads have been deposited in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive under BioProject number PRJNA598862 and run numbers SRX7747184, SRX7747185, SRX7747186 and SRX7747187.

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Table 1. Summary statistics for *Rhodococcus* genomes assembled from Illumina reads

organism	Host	Host common name	Biosample	# contigs ≥ 500 bp	Large st contig	Total length	GC (%)	Mean coverage	N50	CD S	tRNA	tmRNA	GenBank Accession (Assembly)	GenBank Accession (Raw reads)
<i>Rhodococcus fascians</i> GS6	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	Bitter almond	SAMN13734959	86	318389	5427417	64.56	40.6029	120644	5112	51	1	JAAFYX00000000	SRX7747184
<i>Rhodococcus fascians</i> SB10	<i>Prunus persica</i> x <i>Prunus amygdalus</i>	Garnem rootstock	SAMN13734960	99	352664	5508857	64.39	54.8541	133430	5158	50	1	JAAFYW00000000	SRX7747185
<i>Rhodococcus</i> sp. B10	<i>Iresine herbestii</i> Hook.	Herbst's bloodleaf	SAMN13734961	88	338193	5469932	65.11	109.753	112702	5154	51	1	JAAFYV00000000	SRX7747186
<i>Rhodococcus kroppenstedtii</i> K5	<i>Pistacia vera</i> L. cv. Mateur	Pistachio	SAMN13734962	131	168870	4030995	70.26	84.8393	57161	3697	51	1	JAAFYU00000000	SRX7747187